

Diazoalkanes. Part I. Reaction of Diazomethane with Methyl Ether of Cyclic Hydroxymethyleneketones

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Methyl ethers of cyclic α -hydroxymethyleneketones (β -oxoaldehydes) have been found to react with diazomethane leading to Δ^1 -pyrazolines which readily undergo elimination of nitrogen to afford β -methylated products. The latter on hydrolysis furnish α -acetylketones and it thus constitutes a simple method for the preparation of α -acetylketones from the readily accessible β -oxo-aldehydes. A convenient preparation of methyl ether of hydroxymethyleneketones and their probable configuration have also been described. A preliminary account has already been published¹.

It is well-known² that diazomethane reacts with a variety of compounds containing activated double bond, e. g., α , β -unsaturated ketones, aldehydes, and esters with the formation of pyrazoline derivatives. The initial product is a Δ^1 -pyrazoline (I) which subsequently rearranges to more stable Δ^2 -pyrazoline (II) if by so doing a conjugated system results:

It is further known that pyrazolines of the type (I & II), unsubstituted on nitrogen yield methylated olefins (III) together with varying amounts of cyclopropane derivatives when heated or brought into contact with suitable catalysts. A few examples of α , β -unsaturated ketones or esters thus undergoing β -methylation through the intermediacy of pyrazolines are recorded in the literature³⁻⁷. To these we now add a new series of compounds, the methyl ethers of cyclic α -hydroxymethyleneketones which react with diazomethane in a similar fashion.

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The reduction of mercuric chloride to the mercurous state by peroxydisulphate-malate system may be due to the following step (*loc. cit.*)

Further investigations to elucidate the mechanism of the reduction of mercuric chloride by malic acid induced by peroxydisulphate are in progress.

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